

UZBEKISTAN'S PARTICIPATION IN REGIONAL INTEGRATION PROCESSES AND ITS IMPACT ON INTEGRATION INTO THE WORLD ECONOMY

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Economic integration is an arrangement among nations that typically includes the reduction or elimination of trade barriers and the coordination of monetary and fiscal policies. Economic integration aims to reduce costs for both consumers and producers and to increase trade between the countries involved in the agreement. Economic integration is sometimes referred to as regional integration as it often occurs among neighboring nations. Currently, there is much support from the government of Uzbekistan for regional integration. Since the Independence Day Uzbekistan has been a member of the regional integrational group, Common Independent States. However, it is not enough for countries to be a member of only one integration group as regional integrations are the main components of economic growth and economic development. Although there was much effort for joining in WTO, Eurasian economic union, the government failed to join them as there were many barriers in their economic policy.

Economic policy of the Government of Uzbekistan has reflected its gradualism approach from a transition to a market economy. As mentioned in the years immediately following independence the Government instituted a series of reforms aimed at gradually liberalizing prices, unifying foreign exchange markets, instituting new taxes, lowering import tariffs, and privatizing small shops and residential housing, but it retained control over some prices over levels of production, investment, and trade in line with the earlier Soviet model. The stabilization and structural reform program of the mid-1990s was followed by a reversal of earlier macroeconomic policies, and the Government instituted a multiple currency exchange rate system and embarked upon an import substitution program that included restrictions on current account transactions with direct import controls. In the early part of this decade, the Government worked with the IMF to institute a Staff Monitored Program (SMP) in an effort to stabilize the economy and accelerate the transition to a market economy.

The economic policy of the first president of Uzbekistan was a protective policy that mainly focused on protecting its local manufacturers from the big companies of the world. There are several requirements of WTO and Eurasian economic unions for their members. In order to be a member of these integrations there should be negotiations relating to foreign trade. Governments use the organization to establish, revise, and enforce the rules that govern international trade. Joining in regional integrational groups means to facilitate trade in goods, services and intellectual properties among participating countries by signing bilateral or multilateral agreements that aims to reduce, eliminate or decrease tariffs, quotas and other restrictions. However, during the economic policy of the first president, government of Uzbekistan could not join neither in Eurasian economic union, nor WTO as there were too many tariffs, quotas, and restrictions for importing goods, services, and intellectual properties.

The second reason why Uzbekistan could not join in the regional integrational group is a currency policy. Till 2017 it was difficult to convert Uzbek soums to other currencies as it was not possible to convert currencies in banks. Consequently, many transnational and multinational corporations did not opt for opening their subsidiaries in Uzbekistan. It was risky to open their subsidiaries in Uzbekistan, as they could not take their income from the country. To be more precise, they could not convert their income that earned within country to US dollars. Therefore, they did not commence their manufacturing in this country. There were too many other restrictions for joining regional integrational groups.

Currently, Uzbekistan is about to join in Eurasian economic union. After the election of the second president Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the process of joining in integrational groups accelerated significantly. Free currency conversion is implemented. Namely, government gave an opportunity for every manufacturer to convert soums to other currencies without restrictions.

Nowadays, joining to integrational groups is becoming actual theme of the republic as it enhances the marketplace for uzbek goods and services. Moreover, Since Uzbekistan is a member of CIS, the main trade partners of Uzbekistan are the countries that are within these groups. In the first diagram, it is visible that the biggest importer of uzbek goods and services are Russian Federation, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Ukraine that are the member of CIS. It means that if Uzbekistan joins to more integration groups, the more trade

turnover will be done with them. Therefore, integrational groups will be in priority in economic growth and in economic development.

1-diagram. Top 10 trade partners of Uzbekistan.¹

Top 10 Export Countries

Country	Export USD\$
Russia	\$2,034,723,460
China	\$1,762,654,355
Kazakhstan	\$1,205,703,958
Turkey	\$1,122,701,798
Kyrgyzstan	\$634,433,775
Afghanistan	\$455,262,655
Iran	\$208,512,589
Tajikistan	\$190,180,651
Ukraine	\$113,627,658
Pakistan	\$93,752,686

Top 10 Import Countries

Country	Import USD\$
China	\$5,052,436,029
Russia	\$3,974,192,820
South Korea	\$2,524,586,334
Kazakhstan	\$1,897,813,583
Turkey	\$1,296,307,847
Germany	\$884,163,793
United States	\$498,020,796
Lithuania	\$441,930,892
Turkmenistan	\$401,272,032
Japan	\$381,283,098

If Uzbekistan joins to Eurasian economic union, the country will adjust its economic policy to the general economic policy. In other words, its policy will be almost similar to the economic policy of the member countries. Currently, government is adjusting its custom policy to other members customs` policy even though it is not the member of the union. It is reducing or eliminating tariffs. For example, country eliminated excise tax for imported cars.

In conclusion, Uzbekistan has not yet realized its full potential for exports because of continued import substitution policies and exchange controls that have inhibited free trade and the efficient allocation of resources in the economy. Moreover, exports continue to be concentrated in a few numbers of products with that are characterized by fairly volatile world markets and relatively stagnant growth prospects. Exports have also been directed towards CIS countries that are also experiencing adjustment problems. Finally, the lack of an incentive structure, combined with exchange restrictions and heavy tax penalties, have further hampered the country's export growth performance. Under these circumstances, it is unlikely that exports will be the country's engine of growth in the medium to long term, and economic growth will be limited to developments in its relatively small domestic market. Therefore, these barricades should be alleviated so as to achieve economic development.

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